

Prediction of Different Learning Habit among Students using Data Mining Algorithms

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Abstract—Education is really important. Data mining is useful for forecasting a student's academic achievement. This study focuses on identifying distinct learning habits among students and using data mining algorithms to predict academic success, leading to the prediction of the optimum learning habit. The use of Naive Bayes, J48 employing WEKA as an Open Source Tool is used to predict learning habits. A comparison is also done between these two classifiers in order to estimate accuracy and identify the best learning habits among them.

Keywords—WEKA, Student's learning habits, Academic Performance, Naive Bayes, J48

I. INTRODUCTION

Educational Data Mining is the abbreviation for Educational Data Mining. It can be characterized as a method for locating specific sorts of data from the educational system and applying those methods to better understand students and the system. The process of converting raw data from educational systems into valuable data that can be utilized to make data-driven decisions is referred to as EDM. Many companies benefit from data mining approaches because they can operate on large data sets to identify hidden patterns and linkages, which helps them make data-driven decisions. For information discovery from databases, a variety of approaches and algorithms are utilized.

This study looks at how different learning habits affect a student's academic performance aiming to improve educational quality. The accuracy of several classification techniques is also investigated in this research. The primary goal of this research is to identify the most effective learning habits among students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study looks at how to anticipate a student's learning patterns based on their hearing, writing, and reading abilities. They used a variety of data mining approaches to compare accuracy based on student characteristics. A thorough analysis on the data set was undertaken to determine the goodness of a predictor using two individual classifiers J48 (J48) and Naive Bayes.

Data mining is an emerging technique that is currently being applied in a variety of fields, including student educational and learning analytics, according to Paper [1].

Authors listed in [2] Educational Data Mining (EDM) is an interdisciplinary topic of research that uses machine learning, statistics, Data Mining (DM), psycho-pedagogy, information retrieval, cognitive psychology, and recommender systems methodologies and techniques to tackle educational problems.

The major goal of this study is to find the optimum feature selection and classification algorithms for studying various learning habits in schools. The objective is to find the best learning habits by comparing classification algorithms such as Naive Bayes and J48 using WEKA tool. The idea behind this research work is to identify learning habit which help the faculties to give special attention to individual student's to improve their overall performance.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Using the students' performance dataset developed for the study, the performance of several feature selection methods was examined on different classification algorithms in this research effort. Several comparisons were done in the proposed study to assess the effectiveness of feature selection strategies utilizing measurements involving error and accuracy metrics.

The study's overall goal was to assess the usefulness of several algorithms in predicting distinct learning habits and, as a result, measuring academic success. Aside from academic performance, other characteristics were assessed using dummy data to measure the student's total success.

The main goal of this research is to look at the student data that is accessible at the college and see if there are any patterns that can be used to predict their success. The study's specific goal is to classify students based on their academic performance as well as other criteria outside than academic performance.

IV. ABOUT WEKA TOOL

The data mining strategy is implemented using the WEKA 3.6.13 tool, which is a collection of machine learning algorithms for data mining tasks. The algorithms can be applied on a dataset directly or called from Java code. Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis, developed at the University of Waikato, New Zealand, is free software licensed under the GNU General Public License (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Weka tool

V. CLASSIFIERS USED IN WEKA

A. Using J48 algorithm

The J48 algorithm is one of the greatest machine learning algorithms for categorizing and continuously examining data. When employed for example, it takes up more memory and reduces the speed and precision with which it classifies medical data. It's a more advanced variant of ID3.

J48 adds some new features, such as accounting for missing values, decision tree pruning, rule derivation, and so on. It's a Java implementation of the C4.5 algorithm that's free source.

Figure 2: J48 algorithm

B. Using Naïve Bayes algorithm

For the classification problem, it is a well-designed algorithm. When we utilize this approach for text-based data analysis, such as Natural Language Processing, we can get fantastic results (NLP). There is a presumption that one characteristic and its value are unrelated to other features and their values. The Nave Bayes method is a supervised learning technique for addressing classification issues that is based on the Bayes theorem.

VIII. RESULTS

The dataset during this work is tested and analyze with two Classification algorithms those are Naïve Bayes and J48 (using training set). All the statistics results are provided in Table 1. Also a comparison of accuracy of all classifiers is done and finally it has been investigated that Naïve Bayes technique performs best with accuracy 94.06%.

Figure 3: Naïve Bayes algorithm

VI. IMPLEMENTATION USED

The method proposed in this paper for identifying various learning habits is part of the Data Mining process. The four stages of this methodology are dataset gathering, preprocessing, data mining (classification), and interpretation. Data collection is the process of gathering all available information on students while taking into account various factors in order to predict the best learning habits.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The datasets for this study are saved as .arff (Attribute - Relation File Format) files. An .arff file is a text file in ASCII format that describes a list of types and their values. This file is formatted in a specified way. Weka can only operate with .arff files, so once you've saved it, you'll need to convert it to that format.

ARFF files are divided into two sections. The header information is presented first, followed by the data information. The relation name, a list of attributes, and their types are all found in the header. For different types of data, different attribute types can be used.

Figure 4: Output

IX. CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

Classification algorithms are used in this study to predict student learning habits from a set of student data. A model was created in this study based on some selected student-related input variables acquired from the real world (college) as well as factors not linked to college data. With 94.06% accuracy, Nave Bayes is the most accurate data mining classifier, and it proves to be a potentially effective and efficient classifier method. This study will assist schools in identifying distinct learning habits among students, which will serve as a foundation for determining particular assistance for them.

In the future, certain new elements could be used to increase student performance, with results based on yearly data. On this data, other data mining techniques like k-means, clustering algorithms, and other classification methods can be used.

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